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Fish species population dynamics of Dadin – Kowa Reservoir applying Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK)

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on the application of indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) of local fishermen to determine fish species dynamics overtime at the commercial landing sites of Dadin – Kowa Reservoir, Gombe State, Nigeria. Semi – structured questionnaire with demographic, gears used and ecological components was applied. Findings revealed the dominance of male fishermen with 50% within the age group of 20 – 40 years old. Whereas only 12.5% had attended some certain level of tertiary education. Gears used were net – derived with 43.05% using non – selective dragnet (Taru) and only 16.6% used hook & line. Peak recruitment season were quantized to the months of June – October with *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Alestes dentex* and *Bagrus bayad macropterus* being dominant fish species. All respondents adjudicated the decline of fish species overtime while 8.33% inferred stock depression is associated with fish behavioral change. Twenty (20) were locally extinct including key players such as *Heterotis niloticus*, *Parachanna obscura* and *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*. The incorporation of locals can aid immensely to improvement and management of fish stock.

Keywords:- TEK, stock depression, Reservoir, Fish behavioral change, *Parachanna obscura*.

INTRODUCTION

Ecosystems sustain themselves in a dynamic balance based on cycles and fluctuations, which are non-linear processes, therefore ecological awareness then will arise only when rational knowledge is combined with an intuition for the nonlinear nature of our environment. Such intuitive wisdom is a characteristic of traditional non-literature cultures in which life is organized around a highly refined awareness of the environment (Alangui *et al.*, 2020). Rural settlements where population is dependent on agricultural practices such as fisheries; have developed closed relationship with the local environment. Such interaction maybe expressed in local and traditional knowledge, (such as beliefs, land use, practice

and intangible forms of heritage) but as well as tangibly in the adaptive management of natural resources including fish (Iuga *et al.*, 2013). Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) was first introduced in 1980's as a means to raise awareness of the existence and value of the indigenous knowledge in conservation efforts and to ensure equity to its treatment; especially in the context of scientific theories and methods (Isaac *et al.*, 2018). It is stated that indigenous people and their communities have a vital role in environmental management and development because of their knowledge and traditional practices (Iuga *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, states should recognize and duly support their identity, culture and interest and enable their effective participation in the achievement of sustainable development (Utomo, 2010). According to Paquet (2015), the wildlife managers and researchers are incorporating and embracing information from cultural knowledge. However, indigenous human communities that have direct cultural connections to local ecology and place are drawing upon information from environmental research. The mutual recognition is that although, western science and TEK constitute different paths to knowledge, they are rooted in the same reality and affirm one another (Paquet, 2015).

Therefore; TEK can be defined as “a cumulative body of knowledge, practice and belief about the relationship of living beings (especially humans) with one another and their environment, thus this evolves by adaptive processes and it is handed down through generations by cultural transmission (Paquet, 2015).” Oftentimes, TEK is a part of an indigenous world view or value (Rossier and Lake, 2016) or however, LEK (Local Ecological Knowledge) or TEK is an experiential, adaptive, practice-based learning and accumulation of relevant knowledge by people who depend strongly on ecosystems. Therefore the continuity of local ecological knowledge system depends on the institutional capacities of communities to access and manage resources including fish (Dey *et al.*, 2020). But TEK or LEK is ubiquitous by definition; therefore, to address this, a consensus had been attained and thus accomplished this complexity which includes: (1) linked to a specific place, culture or society (2) dynamic in nature (3) belongs to groups of people who live in close contact with natural systems (4) contrast with modern or western formal scientific knowledge (Utomo, 2010).

Traditional Ecological Knowledge bears prominent branches to aid the understanding and due application of its methodologies; these branches include

- (1) TEK as a perception of nature, which includes theories, frameworks, and examples for understanding how to perceive and categorize nature and the area of “ethno taxonomy”.
- (2) The second branch of TEK is the use of nature; also referred to as “ethno ecology” which considers how people perceive, store and use local natural resources, which resources are important for livelihoods and what types of management practices are used for resource extraction. Examples include (fishes) targets species such as commercial fishes are more important than others.
- (3) Thirdly; TEK as applicable tool for management, approaches the importance of TEK as driver and contributor to conventional biological knowledge (Fischer *et al.*, 2015)

A lot of other works have been done which contributed to the understanding of Traditional Ecological Knowledge and its applications in the environment; fisheries and management, by Ross, (2019), Barbosa-filho, (2020) on compressor fishing, while Runde *et al.*, (2020) applied TEK methodologies to assess the impacts of hydro-electric power Reservoir construction on the downstream sector.

The management of fisheries exists longtime ago, fisheries by most coastal; riverine and lake dwelling people has been regarded as not only a form of economic perspective but also socio-cultural way of life (Utomo, 2010). The concepts of TEK in fisheries study has encompassed the following categorization such as gear used, spatial areas, effort, fish species and catch. Fishermen have been viewed to hold great deal of knowledge (Fischer *et al.*, 2015) and are information providers. However this knowledge has been transformed globally (Aswani *et al.*, 2018), through scientific monitoring. TEK is well recognized worldwide (Harish *et al.*, 2015) and can enable estimation of historical changes in data-poor inland capture fisheries especially Nigeria (Dey *et al.*, 2020).

Notable works had been conducted applying Traditional Ecological Knowledge across the world with emphasis on fisheries resources management; exploitation and sustainability. This comprised the works of Mesquita and Isaac-Nahum, (2015) who identified different fishing gears used by the locals in the coastal

areas of Brazil, notably includes 12 types of netting, 10 hook and line techniques and 8 spear-fishing techniques. Ornamental fish harvested through free diving and scuba-diving, the nomenclature, capture techniques, fish habitat identification, sex differentiation fish taste, fish price, origin of fish, freshness, processing, preservation and subsequent knowledge transmission of fish was reported from Indonesia (Alfian *et al.*, 2020). The interconnection between fishermen's knowledge and religion with the aim of resource management was reported by (Lowe *et al.*, 2020). TEK methodologies alongside simulation modeling were applied for fishery management; outcomes indicated integrating indigenous knowledge with scientific research is crucial to inform locally relevant fisheries managers (Ban *et al.*, 2017). The advancement of TEK to river restoration as a habitat of fish had been discussed and understood by (Szalkiewicz *et al.*, 2020). The authors concluded that application of TEK has large potential for improving water resources management and restoration of aquatic ecosystems which seems to remain a key factor in a successful future of river restoration. Traditional Socio-Ecological Knowledge (TSEK) had been viewed as an adaptive and complex system of experimental knowledge, practices and beliefs of local people, governing relationships among themselves and with their surrounding ecosystems (Araia and Chirwa, 2019) supportive of this knowledge and its application includes the works of Hosen *et al.* (2020). Inclusive of this matter is the application of TEK on the fish population changes, environmental dynamics and concerns (Brewster *et al.*, 2016). Halim *et al.*, (2020) illustrated the potentials for the transformation of TEK management into contemporary territorial-based fish management policies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 The Study Area

The study was conducted in Dadin-Kowa Reservoir. It is located in Dadin-Kowa Town, Yamaltu-Deba Local Government area, Gombe State in the North east of Nigeria. Dadin-kowa town is located between Latitudes 10°19'19"N and 10.32194°N; Longitude 11°28'54"E and 11.48167°E (Wikipedia, 2023). It shares common boundary with Akko Local Government area, to the South and West, Yamaltu-Deba to the East and Kwami to the North. Dadin-kowa has an altitude of about 370 meters above sea level. It is a residential and commercial area with such amenities as schools, Motor Park, market etc.

The study area is characterized by two distinct climates, the dry season (November–March) and the rainy season (April–October) with an average rainfall of 850mm and the mean annual temperature is about 32°C. As in other part of Nigerian savanna, the precipitation distribution is mainly triggered by a seasonal shift of the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) (Ibeje and Okoro, 2013; Uloko *et al.*, 2019). The dry season comes with the Northeastern trade wind over the region originating from Sahara belt, the wind is dry and dust laden accompanied by low-pressure system. The wet season comes with the south-westerly wind which is moisture laden and originates from high pressure zone over the Atlantic Ocean to the low pressure zone over the Sahara (Noel *et al.*, 2020).

Dadin-Kowa Dam (Reservoir) is located 5km North of Dadin-Kowa village (about 37km from Gombe Town, along Gombe-Biu Road) in Yamaltu-Deba local Government Area of Gombe State. The Reservoir was completed in 1984 and is a major source of water for drinking, irrigation, hydro power generation (with a potential of 39 MW) and fishing activities in Gombe town, Gombe State (Jesse *et al.*, 2019). It is part of River Gongola (Ja'afaru and Abubakar, 2015) and considered the second largest Reservoir in Nigeria (Chellube *et al.*, 2018). The maximum flood level is 249m above sea level (a.s.l), a maximum supply level of 247m (a.s.l) and minimum supply of 239 m (a.s.l). The surface area of the reservoir is 300 km². The 1:10,000-year peak in-flow is 3160 m³/sec, and the peak outflow is 1110 m³/sec. The total catchment area of the Gongola River is approximately 56,000 km³, 58.5% of which lies upstream of the Reservoir. It also has a gated overflow crest open chute bucket spillway with a maximum design discharge of 1,110 m/sec at reservoir maximum flood level and three (3) radial gates (Uloko *et al.*, 2019). Its drainage basin is situated in North-Eastern Nigeria, with water capacity of 800 million cubes and surface area of 300 kilometers square (Ja'afaru and Abubakar, 2015).

Figure 1: Map of Dadin-Kowa showing sampling sites

Source: Google maps (2023)

Questionnaire Interviews for Fishermen’s Ecological Knowledge on Fish Population Dynamic

Semi-structured interviews were conducted to willing fishermen and their responses were analyzed. Adult fisher-folks, including veteran fishers wherever possible, were approached and a short account of what the

research is all about and what is expected from them was explained (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018). Consent of the interviewees was sought before commencing the interview. Efforts were made not to disrupt their fishing activities.

Table I: Interviews for fishermen’s ecological knowledge on fish population dynamic

Date:

A. Demographics

1. Name of respondent:
2. Age:
(10-20) (21-30) (31-40) (41-50) (51-60) (61-Above)
3. Gender:
a. Male b. Female c. others (specify)
4. Marital status:
a. single b. married c. divorce d. widow e. widower
5. Educational status (both western and religious):
a. Formal education (i. Primary, ii. Secondary, iii. Tertiary)
b. Non-formal (i. Islam education, ii. Nomadic education)
6. Religion:
A. Islam B. Christianity C. Traditional religion D. Others (specify.....)
7. Number of children:
8. Ethnicity and Tribe:
9. Residence (in terms of proximity to the water body):

B. Fishing Gears Aspects

10. Duration of fishing activities (Active fishing years):
11. Type of fishing (full time or part time basis)
12. Type of fishing gear used:
A. Mesh Net, B. Lift Net, C. Cast Net, D. Hook and Line, E. Cages, F. Set Net, G. Trap
13. Nature of the fishing gear:
A. Active B. Passive
14. Cost of the gear:
15. Usage on which fish species:
16. Effectiveness of the gear:
17. Seasonal usage of gear:
A. All year round B. Dry season C. Rainy season D. Harmattan period
18. Mesh size:
19. Hook size:
20. Hours of fishing:

C. Ecological Aspects

21. Dominant fish species encountered and at which season (rainy, dry and Harmattan):
22. Catches according to fishing season:
23. Recruitment percentage by seasons:
24. Volume of catch per fishing season (young, adult, gravid and dead fish):
25. Current status of fish (Any changes in harvest):
26. Awareness on decrease of fish stock:
A. Yes Aware, B. No Unaware, C. Others (Specify)
27. Reasons for decrease of fish stock:
A. Gears Used B. Gear’s Mesh Size, C. Poison Usage, D. Seasonality, E. Others

3.10 Data Analysis

Data obtained from the responses of the interviewed fishermen were assessed using simple percentages and chart.

RESULTS

3.1 Demographical description of the fishermen in Dadin-Kowa Dam

The demographic responses are presented in Table 2. The table indicates that 50% of the respondents are within the age range of 20 – 40 years old. The rest constituted the elderly within the ages of 61 years and above (Table 2). Reflecting on to the gender constitution, all the respondents are males (100%). Seventy – five (75) percent are married. Educational statuses of the respondents indicated that 62.5% had primary education, while 25% had attended secondary school and only twelve (12.5) percent had some level of tertiary education (Table 2). Reflecting to the proximity; all the respondents with the exception of inhabitants of Malleri study site have close proximity to the main water body and its tributaries (67%). Most of the respondents are fulltime fishermen (73%) while a relatively small fraction (27%) are part – time fishermen. Active fishing years indicated that 31% of the respondents have active fishing years within the range of 11 – 20 years; and 21 -30 years constituted 33% which are the peak active fishing durations (Table 2).

3.2 Fishing gears used by the fishermen in Dadin-Kowa Dam

The fishing gears used by the fishermen identified is presented on Table 2. The fishing gears used are basically nets, derivatives of nets, and hook and line. However most of them are known by their local names such as the Taru (Dragnet), Burgi (Lift – net) which are nets, and actively used (Table 3). Whereas Kalgana, Buzuwa and Undusu which are cages (net – derived) and Qugiya (Hook and line). A total of 31 respondents (43.05%) used dragnet (Taru), whereas 27.77% applied lift – net, 12 individuals (16.66%) utilize hook and line and only 12.5% employed cages for fishing (Table 3).

3.3 Fish species recruitment strengths according to the respondents

Fish species recruitment peaks showed that *Oreochromis niloticus* has peak occurrence in the months of June, September and October. However, this is similar to that of *Alestes dentex*. This are considered the highest recruitments peaks. But however, a few of the fish species can be available in the rainy season. But mostly *Oreochromis niloticus*, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Citharinus citharus*, *Hydrocynus brevis* and *Bagrus bayad* are the abundant fish species during the rainy season.

Table 2: Demographical description of the fishermen in Dadin-Kowa Dam

Variable	Category	Percentage
Age (years)	20 to 40	50
	41 to 60	33
	61 and above	17
Gender	Male	100
	Female	0
Marital status	Single	25
	Married	75
Formal Educational status	Primary education	62.5
	Secondary education	25
	Tertiary	12.5
Non-formal education status	Islamic education	93
	Christian education	7
Proximity to waterbody	Closed proximity	67
	Distant proximity	33
Type of fishing	Full – time	73.6
	Part – time	26.3
Active fishing duration (Years)	1 – 10	19
	11 – 20	31
	21 – 30	33
	31 – 40	17

Table 3: Fishing gears used by the fishermen in Dadin-Kowa Dam

Variable	Category	Frequency	Respondents' Percentage
Fishing gears used	Dragnet (Taru)	31	43.05
	Lift-net (Burgi)	20	27.77
	Cages	9	12.50
	Hook and line	12	16.66

3.4 Ecological factors influencing fish species abundance according to the respondents

All the respondents (100%) examined acknowledged that there is change in fish stock abundance overtime. The ecological responses of the respondents regarding factors influencing fish abundance is presented on Figure 2. The figure illustrated that 43.05% of the respondents thought that fish stock depression is associated with *Non – Selective Gears* usage. While 18 respondents (25%) indicated that *Many resources users* but 10 (13.88%) respondents said that fish stock decline is associated with *Poor government supervision*. The rest of the respondents 7 (9.72%) and 6 (8.33%) adjudicated that fish stock depression is as a result of *damming* and *seasonality* as well as *poor gears used and fish behavioral change overtime* (Figure 2).

4.5 Locally disappearing fish species according to the respondents

Locally disappearing fish species as stated by the fishermen is presented on Table 4. The table indicates a total of twenty (20) fish species which have disappeared locally. Eleven (11) were identified but the remaining nine (9) were not identified and only to be known by their local names. A total frequency of 63 respondents (87.50%) reported the local disappearance of *Heterotis niloticus* (Bargi) and *Parachanna obscura* (Dunu), while 56 respondents constituting 77.78% reported that of *Synodontis membraneus*. The table showed that fifty – two (52) fishermen recorded the loss of *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*. However; only 12 respondents recorded that of *Lates niloticus* and *Gymnarchus niloticus*. The rest of the fish species inclusive of Karuda, Loro (*Scarus ghobban*), Amangaza, Mai damusa, Sham-sham (*Synodontis membraneus*), Wako, Kiraji, Gaiwa (*Protopterus annectens*), Muzine, Bankoro, Abus, Maitaitaka, Maitawada (*Synodontis nigrita*) were reported to be locally lost by three (3) elderly respondents (4.16%) accordingly (Table 4).

Figure 2: Reasons for the decline of fish stock diversity of Dadin-Kowa Dam.

Table 4: Locally disappearing fish species according to the respondents

S/n	Local names	Scientific names	Respondents' Frequency	Respondents' percentage (%)
1.	Bargi	<i>Heterotis niloticus</i>	63	87.50
2.	Barya	<i>Lates niloticus</i>	12	16.67
3.	Yauni	<i>Gymnarchus niloticus</i>	12	16.67
4.	Farin-kurungu	<i>Synodontis membraneus</i>	56	77.78
5.	Dunu	<i>Parachanna obscura</i>	63	87.50
6.	Kausa (ciciyawa)	<i>Distichodus rostratus</i>	60	83.34
7.	Jari	<i>Heterobranchus bidorsalis</i>	52	72.23
8.	Karuda	NF	3	4.16
9.	Loro	<i>Scarus ghobban</i>	3	4.16
10.	Amangaza	NF	3	4.16
11.	Mai damusa	NF	3	4.16
12.	Sham-sham (Golaki)	<i>Synodontis membraneus</i>	3	4.16
13.	Wako	NF	3	4.16
14.	Kiraji	NF	3	4.16
15.	Gaiwa	<i>Protopterus annectens</i>	3	4.16
16.	Muzine	NF	3	4.16
17.	Bankoro	NF	3	4.16
18.	Abus	NF	3	4.16
19.	Maitsitaka	NF	3	4.16
20.	Maitawada	<i>Synodontis nigrita</i>	3	4.16

NF: Generic name(s) Not Found

DISCUSSION

4.1 Demographic parameters of the fishermen from Dadin – Kowa Dam.

In this study, a total of 31 respondents (50%) are within the age range of 20 – 40 years old. This result is similar to the outcome of the works reported by Harisha *et al.*, (2016) from India, Wiryono *et al.*, (2019) and (Ngodigha and Gbarabe, 2015) from Niger – Delta. The age composition depicts the natural settings of human development in which the most active members are individuals within this age brackets.

The gender structure of the respondents from this study indicated a 100% dominance of the male gender regardless of age. This outcomes is similar to that of Ahmad *et al.*, (2018) from Challawa Reservoir, Kano State and Berkström *et al.* (2019). Fishing activities is an act that requires minimal fear and agile strength which are rare in the female. However; such activities are considered a taboo in some traditions which might have been the possible reason for poor participation of the female gender.

The marital status composition of the study sites in this study indicated that 75% of the respondents are married and with children. Similar outcome was reported by Berkström *et al.* (2019) where 74% are married and Ahmad *et al.*, (2018) from Challawa. Many rural settlers have been understood to get married at early age which involve minimal financial burden unlike urban centers. This assertion is applicable to the Dadin – Kowa settlers.

The overwhelming majority of the respondents had attended primary schools (62.5%) and only 9 (12.5%) individuals attended some levels of tertiary education. This stratified composition is similar to the outcome of Ngodigha *et al.*, (2015). It is observed as individuals attained more levels of educational qualifications; their job preferences shift from the menial jobs such as the crude fishing activities to a white-collar job. This scenario is similar to both rural as well as urban settlements.

With the exception of Malleri study site, all the respondents (67%) are within closed proximity to the main waterbody and its' tributaries. This is attributable to the different geographical position of those settlements in relation to water confinements and low levels of urbanization (rural expansion). Farmlands situated near the waterbody can be irrigated, as such cannot be easily converted to houses due to their economic impacts and fear of possible flooding.

Data from respondent's participation in fishing activities indicated that 53 (73.4%) are full – time fishermen. This result bears similar outcome with that of Ahmad *et al.* (2018) were 72% of the 66 fishermen were full – time fishermen from Challawa Gorge Dam. It is understood that rural life is mostly devoid of abundant white-collar jobs; as such, large number of individuals may resort to fishing not as a hobby but as a full-time job. However, some of the respondents only participate in the fishing activity due to family needs, water availability as well as during holidays. The dry season is mostly associated with few farming activities in rural settlements; this factor also shifts the individuals to partake in fishing activities either on a full-time or part-time basis. But it was noted also that some fishermen are into the art simply because it's a family heritage which passes down to generations. Lack of good government job and poor income at times increase the pool of individuals going into fishing activities.

The active fishing years from this study which ranges between 1-10 years (19%), 11-20 years (31%), 21 – 30 years (33%) and 31 – 40 years (17%) is similar to findings of Ngodigha and Gbarabe, (2015). Those individuals with high fishing experience (17%) might have started fishing at young age and progresses through old age where most activities recede due to aging.

4.2 Identified fishing gears used by the respondents

The findings from this study indicated the dominant usage of nets (Dragnets = 43.05%, and lift-net = 27.77%). This is similar to that of (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018) from Challawa reservoir and Berkström *et al.*, (2019). Aquatic ecosystems have witnessed tremendous structural change in number and habitats due to mainly human induced factors including fishing activities, pollution and urbanization (Gray *et al.*, 2017). Fishing activities involves diverse fishing gears. It can be noted in this study, the non-selective gears (lift-nets and dragnets) are most widely used. This could be due to the high demand of the fish to sustain unsaturated markets, good price of fish stock, and need for high-income generation. The vast majority of the fishermen in this study are married men laden with family liabilities; these liabilities could serve as a yardstick to enhance sources of family income which may include increased fishing pressure employing

more effective, probably illegal and non-selective fishing gears. This is with less or none due regards for the future fish stock abundance and biodiversity.

The other component of the fishermen utilizes selective gears such as the cages and hook and lines. A few individuals mostly by part-time fishers and elderly who have less burdens of life and aging use these gears.

It was understood that tropical aquatic resources users are continuously receiving the impacts of increased human pressures on the tropical inland waters and are experiencing decreasing fish stock abundance with depressed catch size (Berkström *et al.*, 2019). This is as a result of fishing gears used, weak laws on gears and enforcement (Abiaobo, Ekpo, and Asuquo, 2016).

4.3 Fish species recruitment strengths according to the respondents

The season's yield varies with the rainy season being the season with lowest yield and availability besides the Harmattan. The highest yield is observed in the dry season with the possibility of obtaining all the fish species. This type of catch availability and seasonality agrees to the findings of (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018)

The present findings inferred the dominance of cichlids (*Oreochromis niloticus*), Clarids (*Clarias gariepinus*), bagrids (*Bagrus bayad*) and schilbeids (*Schilbe mystus*). The fish species dominance results slightly conformed to the results of Ahmed *et al.*, (2018) and completely coincided with that of (Mshelia *et al.*, 2015). The months of June, September and October were understood to be the months with peak catches of the said fish species as recorded from the fishermen. This is also typical of tropical reservoirs which agrees to the results of Mahmoud *et al.*, (2011) as reported in Ahmad *et al.* (2018).

4.4 Identified factors influencing fish stock decline according to the respondents

Regardless of age – brackets, all the respondents are aware of decline and changes in catch (CPUE) overtime. This was supported with indication of lesser catch in the present time (current years) than the past decades. While the respondents agreed upon this phenomenon, it was also reached that the vast majority of these fishermen asserted that the use of fishing gears with finer or minute mesh sizes (especially mosquito nets) contributed largely to the decline in stock abundance and increased fishing efforts. This assertion has been understood by other researchers as well such as (Linus *et al.*, 2014). But some workers stressed that prey-predator relationship also influenced stock dynamics. Distortion of lower trophic levels has been witnessed to affect higher trophic levels (Bolatito, 2015).

Large volume of resource users (Dadin – Kowa reservoir documents over 200 fishermen), this vastness of resource users also contributed to the depletion of resources. This is in accordance to the findings of (Nayaya *et al.*, 2012).

The present study indicated that 13.88% of the fishermen thought that the fish stock decline is as a result of poor monitoring inclusive of laws and enforcement by relevant governmental agency. Weak laws and enforcement of governmental laws regarding fish stock exploitation had been identified as well by Abiaobo *et al.* (2016). Law enforcement is important for efficient management. However, where the laws are weak or not fully enforced on to the appropriate subjects, it becomes difficult to determine fish stock consistency and sustainability.

Also damming, seasonality, corruption (poor regulation, enforcement and adoption of current scientific technical findings among others), behavioral evolution of fish were understood to be among the growing causes of fish biodiversity depressions (Abdulkarim *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The application of Traditional Ecological Knowledge to understand fish species population dynamics of Dadin – Kowa reservoir provided the basement for incorporation of local fishermen to monitor fish species dynamics giving the atmosphere for effective governmental intervention, planning and regulation. The derived information from this study can be a valuable asset not limited to the government but also useful to other stakeholders.

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